

Database:

Ovid MEDLINE(R) ALL <1946 to December 14, 2021>

#	Query	Results from 14 Dec 2021
1	laminectomy.mp. or exp Laminectomy/	15,700
2	exp Diskectomy, Percutaneous/ or exp Diskectomy/ or discectom*.mp. or diskectom*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	10,535
3	exp Decompression, Surgical/ or (surg* adj3 decompression*).mp.	38,490
4	(spin* adj3 fusion*).mp. or exp Spinal Fusion/	32,665
5	exp Spinal Diseases/su	42,426
6	1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5	90,662
7	neurosurgery.mp. or exp Neurosurgery/	35,274
8	(neurosurgical adj3 procedure*).mp. or exp Neurosurgical Procedures/	207,006
9	orthop?edic*.mp. or exp Orthopedics/	133,484
10	exp Orthopedic Procedures/	334,652
11	(spin* adj3 surg*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	27,418
12	(low adj3 back adj3 pain).mp. or exp Low Back Pain/ or (back adj3 pain).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject	70,075

	heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	
13	radicul*.mp. or exp Radiculopathy/	19,868
14	(spin* adj3 disease*).mp. or exp Spinal Diseases/	148,370
15	spine.mp. or exp Spine/ or (spin* adj3 column*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	233,008
16	(lumbar adj3 vertebra*).mp. or exp Lumbar Vertebrae/	61,828
17	12 or 13 or 14 or 15 or 16	359,060
18	((spine* or spinal* or lumbar*) adj7 (surg* or neurosurg* or orthop?ed*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	51,640
19	telemedicine*.mp. or exp Telemedicine/ or telehealth*.mp. or tele-health*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	48,095
20	telephone*.mp. or exp Telephone/ or (cell adj3 phone*).mp. or exp Cell Phone/ or (mobile adj3 phone*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word,	94,187

	protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	
21	(smartphone* or smart-phone*).mp. or exp Smartphone/ [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	19,103
22	tablet*.mp. or exp Tablets/	65,222
23	(mobile adj3 application*).mp. or exp Mobile Applications/	13,107
24	(tele-rehabilitation* or telerehabilitation* or (tele adj3 rehabilitation*)).mp. or exp Telerehabilitation/ [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	1,696
25	telenurs*.mp. or exp Telenursing/	435
26	((video adj3 conf*) or video-conf* or videoconf*).mp. or exp Videoconferencing/ [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	6,219
27	(health adj3 communica*).mp. or exp Health Communication/ or (medic* adj3 inform*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease	58,178

	supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	
28	(inform* adj3 communicat* adj3 techn*).mp. or exp Medical Informatics Applications/ or (medical* adj3 informatic*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	480,909
29	(informatic* adj3 application*).mp.	3,047
30	((health adj3 inform* adj3 techn*) or (nurs* adj3 inform*)),.mp. or exp Nursing Informatics/ [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	12,790
31	((electronic adj3 health adj3 service*) or ehealth or e-health).mp. adj5 (communicat*.mp. or exp Communication/) [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	1,120
32	((home adj3 visit*) or (house adj3 call*)).mp. or exp House Calls/ [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	13,983
33	(real-time adj3 support*).mp.	907
34	((after adj3 car*) or after-car*).mp. or exp Aftercare/ [mp=title, abstract, original title, name	342,242

	of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	
35	((followup adj3 car*) or (follow-up adj3 car*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	24,098
36	((followup adj3 support*) or (follow-up adj3 support*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	2,522
37	(remote adj3 monitor*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	4,743
38	(active adj3 post-discharge adj3 surveillanc*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	8
39	simulation*.mp. or exp Simulation Training/ [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol	555,553

	supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	
40	((instruction* adj3 film*) or (instruction* adj3 video*)).mp. or exp "Instructional Film and Video"/ [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	1,304
41	exp Pain Management/ or (pain adj3 manag*).mp. or exp Analgesia/ or analgesia*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	145,968
42	(clinic* adj3 teach* adj3 method*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	317
43	((client* adj3 educat*) or (patient* adj3 educat*)).mp. or exp Patient Education as Topic/ [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	124,239
44	(car* adj3 behavior*).mp. or exp Continuity of Patient Care/ or (patient* adj3 car*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol	910,582

	supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	
45	(self-car* or (self adj3 car*)).mp. or exp Self Care/ [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	81,378
46	(health adj3 promot*).mp. or exp Health Promotion/	128,597
47	((multi-disciplin* adj3 car*) or (multidisciplin* adj3 car*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	10,171
48	(self-manag* or (self adj3 manag*)).mp. or exp Self-Management/ [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	28,117
49	recover*.mp. or exp Recovery of Function/	769,343
50	convalescence.mp. or exp Convalescence/ or exp Rehabilitation/ or rehab*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	581,701
51	(mobile adj3 team\$).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word,	946

	keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	
52	(text adj3 messag*).mp. or exp Text Messaging/	6,938
53	((pre-operative adj3 educat*) or (preoperative adj3 educat*) or ((preoperative adj3 exercise*) or prehabilitation*)).mp. or exp Preoperative Exercise/ [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	2,318
54	((emotional adj3 adjust*) or (psychologic* adj3 adjust*) or (adapt* adj3 psychologic*) or (adapt* adj3 physiologic*) or (physiologic* adj3 adjust*)).mp. or Adaptation, Psychological/ or Adaptation, Physiological/ or (adaptive adj3 behavior*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	191,829
55	((short adj3 time adj3 stay*) or (short adj3 term adj3 stay*) or (short adj3 time adj3 hospitalization*) or (short adj3 term adj3 hospitalization*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	924
56	(return* adj3 home*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept	4,451

	word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	
57	(hospital* adj3 home*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	13,378
58	discharg*.mp. or exp Patient Discharge/ [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	307,071
59	(postdischarg* or (post adj3 discharg*) or postdischarg*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	13,131
60	(transition* adj3 home*).mp.	1,363
61	(length* adj3 stay*).mp. or exp Length of Stay/	152,405
62	55 or 56 or 57 or 58 or 59 or 60 or 61	443,354
63	7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11	637,384
64	17 and 63	81,352
65	6 or 18 or 64	134,902
66	19 or 20 or 21 or 22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31 or 32 or 33 or 34 or 35 or 36 or 37 or 38 or 39 or 40 or 41 or 42 or 43 or 44 or 45 or 46 or 47 or 48 or 49 or 50 or 51 or 52 or 53 or 54	3,700,504
67	62 and 65 and 66	2,641

68	limit 67 to (danish or english or norwegian or swedish)	2,493
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